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Formulation and Evaluation of Perindopril Erbumine Buccal Films

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Received 01 May 2011 Received in revised form 10 June 2011 Accepted 12 July 2011 Available online October 2011</p>	<p>The buccal region of the oral cavity is an attractive target for administration of the drug of choice. To increase bioavailability and prevent first pass metabolism of drug, Perindopril Erbumine was embedded in sustained released buccal patch over period of 6 hour. The objective of present work was to characterize the effect of HPMC with Eudragit, sodium CMC and EC for water soluble drug by preparing mucoadhesive buccal patch. Each formulated batch was subjected to various evaluation parameters. The swelling percentage was found to be function of solubility of drug and polymer. The mucoadhesive strength and in-vitro released of water soluble drug through water insoluble HPMC base matrix were found satisfactorily. The physical appearance of buccal patch was examined by scanning electron microscopy. In the present study, attempts were made to prepare and evaluate the Buccal films containing Perindopril hydrochloride, an antihypertensive drug using Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Eudragit RL-100, Eudragit RS-100, Dichloro-Methane, Methanol. The results showed that buccal patches prepared Using 15% propylene glycol w/w of polymer weight was found to have good physical characteristics. A remarkable increase in thickness, FTIR, drug content uniformity, drug release and stability studies percent swelling index, percent moisture uptake and mechanical properties with an increase in the percent hydrophilic polymer (HPMC). All the patches were, thin, smooth and flexible, uniformity in drug content, weight and thickness were observed with their low SD values. In-vitro drug permeation through sheep buccal mucosa was performed using Franz diffusion cells. The film showed maximum permeation at the end of 6 hrs. The release mechanism from all membrane controlled systems followed diffusion mechanism. All the systems were found to be stable with respect to drug content as well as physical changes at 40⁰C and 75% RH.</p>
<p>Keywords Perindopril Erbumine, Eudragit, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Dichloro Methane, Methanol, buccal patches.</p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Amongst the various routes of drug delivery, oral route is perhaps the most preferred to the patient and the clinician alike. However, peroral administration of drugs has disadvantages such as hepatic first pass metabolism and enzymatic degradation within the GI tract, that prohibit the oral administration of certain classes of drugs. Consequently, other absorptive mucosa is considered as potential sites for drug administration.

Transmucosal routes of drug delivery (i.e. the mucosal lining of the nasal, rectal, vaginal, ocular and oral cavity) offer distinct advantages over peroral administration for systematic drug delivery. These advantages include possible bypass of first pass effect, avoidance of pre-systemic elimination within the G.I. tract, and depending on the particular drugs, a better enzymatic flora for drug absorption. The potential irritation and the irreversible damage to the ciliary action of the nasal dosage form as well as the large intra and inter subject variability in mucus secretion in the nasal mucosa, could significantly affect drug absorption from this site.

Even though the rectal, vaginal and ocular mucosa all offer certain advantages, the poor patient acceptability associated with these sites render them reserved for local application rather than systemic drug administration. The oral cavity on the other hand is highly acceptable by patients, the mucosa is relatively permeable with a rich blood supply, it is robust and shows short recovery times after stress or damage and the virtual lack of Langerhans cells makes the oral mucosa tolerant to potential allergens¹.

The oral mucosal drug delivery systems can be localized easily and well accepted by patients. The total surface of the oral cavity is about 100 cm. The mucosal membranes of the oral cavity can be divided into five regions such as the floor of the mouth (sublingual), the buccal mucosa (cheeks), the gums (gingival), palatal mucosa, and the lining of the lips. These oral mucosal regions are different from each other in terms of anatomy, permeability to drug, and their ability to retain a system for a desired length of time. Although the buccal mucosa is less permeable than the sublingual mucosa and it does not yield a rapid onset of action as seen with sublingual

delivery, mucosa of the buccal area has an expanse of smooth and relatively immobile surface, which is suitable for placement of retentive system.

These characteristics make the buccal mucosa a more appropriate site for prolonged systemic delivery of drugs. Perindopril is a prodrug ester of perindoprilat, an ACE inhibitor. This agent has shown pharmacodynamic effects beyond those responsible for lowering blood pressure (BP), including the improvement of endothelial function and the normalisation of vascular and cardiac structure and function.

Perindopril has a well established role in the treatment of patients with hypertension or heart failure. Perindopril erbumine is a nonsulphydryl prodrug that belongs to the angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor class of medications. Perindopril may be used to treat mild to moderate essential hypertension, mild to moderate congestive heart failure, and to reduce the cardiovascular risk of individuals with hypertension or post-myocardial infarction and stable coronary disease⁶.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose – E15 (HPMC E-15), Eudragit RS-100, Eudragit RL-100, Ethyl cellulose and Sodium CMC, Propylene glycol, Dichloro methane, Methanol Sodium hydroxide and Potassium dihydrogen Orthophosphate were obtained as gift samples from Alembic Ltd, Vadodara and all other chemicals/ solvents used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Films

The films were prepared by solvent casting method.

Fabrication of Drug Matrix Device

Accurately weight quantity of polymer hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose, dissolved in 50/50 ethanol and distilled water 5ml. Eudragit RS 100, Eudragit RL100, and Ethyl cellulose dissolved in 2ml ethanol and then dissolved in distilled water up to 5ml. Glycerin in concentration of 30%w/w of polymer was incorporated as plasticizer and accurately weight quantity of drug. Then it is poured over the mercury surface in petridish. The petridish were covered with

funnels to allow controlled evaporation of solvent. These were left undisturbed at room temperature for three to four days

Area of circle = πr^2

Diameter of the plate= 9cm.

Area of the Plate = 63.59 cm²

Diameter of the film = 2.2cm (radius= 2.2/2=1.1cm)

Area of the film = $22/7 \times 1.1 \times 1.1 = 3.799 \text{ cm}^2$

Amount of drug loaded in single film = $63.54/3.799 \times 10 = 167.47 \text{ mg}$

Number of films casted on the rays theoretically = $63.54/ 3.799 = 16 \text{ films}$

Drug incorporated in each film -10mg

Polymer incorporated in each film -600mg

Table 1: Composition of Buccal Patch Formulations

Formulation Code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Drug (mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
HPMC E-15 (mg)	600	450	300	450	300	450	300	450	300
Eu RS100 (mg)	-	150	300	-	-	-	-	-	-
Eu RS100 (mg)	-	150	300	-	-	-	-	-	-
SCMC (mg)	-	-	-	-	-	150	300	-	-
EC (mg)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	150	300
Glycerine (ml)	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12

FC- Formulation Code, Eu RS100- Eudragit RS-100, Eu RL100- Eudragit RL100

Evaluation Tests for Buccal Films

The prepared transdermal films were evaluated for various physic-chemical properties:

- ✓ Physical appearance
- ✓ Weight uniformity
- ✓ Thickness uniformity
- ✓ Assay (drug content uniformity)
- ✓ Moisture absorption
- ✓ Moisture content
- ✓ Surface pH
- ✓ Mechanical properties
- ✓ *Ex vivo* bioadhesive strength
- ✓ *In vitro* release
- ✓ *Ex vivo* permeation of patches

- ✓ Stability studies
- ✓ FTIR studies

Drug-Excipient Interaction Studies (Compatibility Studies (FTIR))

There is always possibility of drug-excipient interaction in any formulation due to their intimate contact. The technique employed in this study is FTIR spectroscopy. IR spectroscopy is one of the most powerful analytical techniques, which offer possibility of chemical identification. The separate IR spectra of Perindopril Erbumine, HPMC, Eudragit RS-100, Eudragit RL-100, Sod CMC and Ethyl Cellulose were obtained.

Fig 1: Perindopril Erbumine

Fig 2: PE+HPMC-E15+EC+NaCMC+ERL-100+ERS-100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile strength

The tensile strength values were calculated using the formula -

$$\text{Tensile strength (kg.mm}^2\text{)} = \frac{\text{Force at break (kg)}}{\text{Initial cross sectional area of the film}}$$

Fig 3: Modified Tensiometer

- A = Pulley
- B = Weighing Pan
- C = Weight
- D = Buccal film

Table 2: Evaluation Test Result- Tensile Strength

Formulation	Tensile Strength (Kg)
F1	8.887
F2	5.074
F3	5.334
F4	4.215
F5	3.714
F6	5.908
F7	5.440
F8	5.172
F9	3.273

In Vitro Release Studies (Diffusion Studies)

Fig. 4: Franz Diffusion Cell

Table 3: Diffusion Studies

Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
15	8.2	6.67	4.38	4.20	6.87	10.8	12.09	7.12	8.4
30	12.1	15.17	12.75	11.9	15.3	23.15	29.0	16.2	19.9
60	25.8	27.5	16.13	22	20.1	35.6	49.7	29.2	27.4
120	34.7	40.1	37.8	33.6	49.6	57.5	65.85	40.7	33.9
180	55.4	63.5	51.25	46.5	68.9	63.24	71.4	52.3	41.4
240	72.5	75.7	63.62	57.1	73.7	72.8	84.7	61.1	55.6
300	80.25	81.24	75.68	79.73	88.46	86.33	94.49	73.97	72.21

The study efforts were to prepare mucoadhesive buccal films of losartan potassium. By using different polymer in different ratios the prepared films were visually translucent and smooth surface. The formulation study targeted to deliver the drug for six hours. The prepared films were subjected to various physicochemical characteristics.

The films varied from 0.107 to 0.226 mm in thickness. The minimum standard deviation values, it assumed that the film's shows uniformity in thickness. All formulations were weighed and they were varied from 50 to 55 mg with minimum standard deviation values. The flexibility of the films were subjected to folding endurance studies; the film was repeatedly folded up to 250 times. It has shows that the films were having good strength for all formulation. The swelling index was higher in formulation F6 and F7, i.e. 25.51 and 26.26 respectively. The surface pH of all films was in range of 5.6 to 6.6 which indicates that surface pH of all formulation was near to neutral pH and no mucosal irritation expected.

The Moisture Loss of all films was recorder which indicates that the moisture loss was maximum for F6 and F7 formulations. The Moisture Absorption of all films was recorder which indicates that the moisture Absorption was maximum for F6 and F7 formulations. The percentage drug content was found to be maximum for F6 and F7 formulations. The bioadhesive strength was found to be maximum for F6 and F7 formulations.

The tensile strength were found for the all the formulation .The force required to break the film strip is more in formulation F1 containing HPMC 4%. IR spectral studies of the formulation films show no interaction between them, hence can be formulated.

CONCLUSION

Development of bioadhesive buccal drug delivery of Perindopril Erbumine is one of the alternative routes of administration to avoid first pass effect and provide prolongs release. A combination of hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose with carboxymethyl cellulose sodium is with complementary physical properties. From the results, it was concluded that the *in vitro* drug release, bioadhesion strength, *ex vivo* residence time of the optimized formulation is suitable for buccal delivery. FTIR studies concluded that there was no interaction between drug and excipients.

REFERENCES

1. C. M. Lehr, J. A. Bouwstra, E. H. Schacht, H. E. Junginger. In vitro evaluation of mucoadhesive properties of chitosan and some other natural polymers. *Int J Pharm* 1992, 78:43-48.
2. D. Solomonidou, K. Cremer, M. Krumme, J. Kreuter. Effect of carbomer concentration and degree of neutralization on the mucoadhesive properties of polymer films. *J Biomater Sci Polym Ed* 2001, 12:1191-1205 ()
3. C. M. Lehr, F. G. J. Poelma, H. E. Junginger, J. J. Tukker. An estimate of turnover time of intestinal mucus gel layer in the rat in situ loop. *Int J Pharm* 1991, 70:235-40.
4. J. F. Forstner. Intestinal mucins in health and disease. *Digestion* 1978, 17:234-63.
5. P. B. van Wachem, T. Beugeling, J. Feijen, A. Bantjes, J. P. Detmers, W. G. van Aken. Interaction of cultured human endothelial cells with polymeric surfaces of different wettabilities. *Biomaterials* 1985, 6:403-8.
6. Martindale – The Complete Drug Reference, 33rd Edition Edited by: Sean C Sweetman Published by Pharmaceutical Press, UK; 2000, 982.

7. Ross and Wilson. *Anatomy & Physiology in Health & Illness*. 9 th Edition, edited by Anne Waugh & Allison Graw Published by Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh; 2001, 289-293.
8. Goodman and Gillman's *The Pharmacological basis of therapeutics*. Published by McGraw Hill, 1999, 2375, 241, 1786.
9. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients*, Edited by: Raymond C Rowe, Paul J Sheskey and Siân C Owen, Page. No 1098-1106.
10. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients*, Edited by: Raymond C Rowe, Paul J Sheskey and Siân C Owen, Page. No 1748-1769.
11. Seyed Alireza Mortazavi. A comparative study between the strength and duration of mucoadhesion of transbuccal carbomer based aqueous gels. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 2002; 1: 7-13.
12. Globodanka Tamburic, Duncan QM Craig. A comparison of different in vitro methods for measuring mucoadhesive performance. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics & Biopharmaceutics* 1997; 44: 159-8.
13. Hirokazu Okamoto, Hiroshisa Taguchi, Kotaro Iida, Kuzumi Danjo. Development of polymer film dosage forms of lidocaine for buccal administration-1. Penetration rate and release rates. *Journal of Controlled Release* 2001; 77: 253-7.

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